

Reports of Projects and Publications Resulting from Projects

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Council on Library Resources, Inc.

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Reports of Projects and Publications Resulting from Projects

Acquisition

Cooperative: The Farmington Plan

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2. Association of Research Libraries: *Farmington Plan Survey, Directed by Robert Vosper & Robert Talmadge, University of Kansas Libraries. Final Report, Presented at the Annual Meeting of ARL, Chicago January 2, 1959.* [Lawrence, Kansas, 1958.] Various pagination: [11] pp., printed; [308] 1., processed.

3. Talmadge, Robert L.: "The Farmington Plan Survey; an Interim Report". *College and Research Libraries* 19:375-383, September 1958.

60. Williams, Edwin E.: *What Is the Farmington Plan?* [Cambridge, Farmington Plan Committee of the Association of Research Libraries: December, 1959]. 4 pp.

74. Vosper, Robert. "Farmington Redivivus: or Ten Years of Co-ordinated Foreign Book Procurement in the U. S.," *Aslib Proceedings* 11: 327-334. December 1959.
Exchanges: The United States Book Exchange, Inc.

4. Williams, Edwin E.: *A Serviceable Reservoir; Report of a Survey of the United States Book Exchange*. Washington: The United States Book Exchange, Inc., 1959. 81 pp.
Foreign Publications

61. Graves, Mortimer. "A First Anniversary Report of Progress on the Implementation of the Dingell Amendment To Public Law 480 (Title I, Section 104n)," [American Council of Learned Societies] *ACLS Newsletter* 10: 8-12. November 1959.

Book-Charging Procedures

62. John Diebold & Associates, Inc.: *Preliminary Study of Library Circulation Systems for the Council on Library Resources, October 1959*. The Corporation, 1959. 31 l., processed.

Book-Selection for College Libraries

5. *Meeting to Explore Some Current and Anticipated Problems in the Building of Book Collections in College Libraries, Edgewater Beach Hotel, Chicago, Illinois, April 20-21, 1959*. [Washington: Council on Library Resources, Inc., 1959] 10.1., processed.

6. "Report on Conference". *Library Journal*, 84:1765-1767. June 1, 1959. (Report on the meeting of April 20-21, 1959.)

Cataloging

"Cataloger's Camera"

7. Radio Corporation of America. Development Engineering Marketing, Defense Electronic Products: *Final Report. Automatic Enlarging Instant Copy Camera, April 6, 1959*. [Camden: The Corporation, 1959] 6 l., 4 pl., processed.

"Cataloging in Source"

8. Osborn, Andrew D.: *Cataloging at the Source; an Opportunity for Cooperation Between the Four Major Book Arts*. Chicago: American Library Association, 1958. 18 l., typescript.

9. U. S. Library of Congress. Processing Department: "Cataloging in Source." *Cataloging Service*. 48:1-3, September 1958; 50:1-4, November 1958; 53:1-17, June 1959.

International Coordination of Cataloging Rules

10. International Federation of Library Associations. International Cataloging Conference: *Bulletin*, 1 London: IFLA Working Group on Co-ordination of Cataloging

Principles, November 1958. Irregular, processed.

11. Osborn, Andrew D.: "At a German Library Association Conference." *ALA Bulletin*, 51: 773-5. November, 1957. [Account of the meeting of the German Library Association (Verein Deutscher Bibliothekare) in Lübeck in June 1957 by the American Library Association's representative.]

12. — —: "Zur Revision der Instruktionen für die Katalogisierung an Amerikanischen Bibliotheken; Vortrag, Gehalten auf dem Bibliothekartag in Lübeck am 13 Juni 1957. (Gekürzt)" *Zeitschrift für Bibliothekswesen und Bibliographie* 4:241-246, 1957.

63. IFLA [International Federation of Library Associations]. "International Cataloguing Conference, Preliminary Meeting, London, July 19th-25th, 1959, Report," *Libri* 9: 254-261. 1959.

Persian Works

13. Sharify, Nasser: *Cataloging of Persian Works, Including Rules for Transliteration, Entry and Description*. Chicago: American Library Association, 1959. xiv, 161 pp.

Closed-Circuit TV in a Decentralized Library Situation

14. Bristol, Roger: *Card Turner Problems: A Preliminary Investigation of the Feasibility of Long-Distance Consultation of Card Catalogs*. Charlottesville: Alderman Library, University of Virginia, 1958. 12 l., processed.

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16. — —: *Closed-Circuit TV Equipment as Used in a Decentralized Library Situation*. Charlottesville: Alderman Library, University of Virginia, 1958. 13 l., processed.

17. — —: *Microcard Images Transmitted by Closed-Circuit TV*. Charlottesville: Alderman Library, University of Virginia, 1958. 6 l., processed.

18. — —: *Page Turners: A Report of Their Usefulness for a Closed-Circuit TV Project*. Charlottesville: Alderman Library, University of Virginia, 1958. 14 l., processed.

19. Gibson, Frank Kenneth: *Closed-Circuit TV at the University of Virginia: A Summary Report*. Charlottesville: Alderman Library, University of Virginia, 1959. 7 l., processed.

20. University of Virginia. Bureau of Public Administration: *A Report on an Experiment Involving the Use of Closed-Circuit TV in a Decentralized Library Situation*. [Charlottesville] The Bureau, 1958. v, 31 l., pl., processed.

Cooperative Centralized Processing of Books

21. Dennis, Willard K.: "Southwest Missouri Library Service, Inc.," *Missouri Library Association Quarterly*, 18:119-123. December, 1957.

22. Kenney, Brigitte L.: "Centralized Processing — Missouri Style," *Library Resources and Technical Services*, 2:185-198. Summer, 1958.

23. — —: *Cooperative Centralized Processing, A Report of the Establishment and First Year of Operation of the Southwest Missouri Library Service, Inc.* Chicago, American Library Association, 1959. 98 pp.

24. Mahoney, Orcena: "An Experiment in Cooperative Processing," *ALA Bulletin*, 52:127-130. February, 1958.

Deterioration of Book-Stock — Causes and Remedies

25. Barrow, William J.: *Physical Strength of Non-Fiction Book Papers, 1900-1949. A Preliminary Report, December 1, 1957.* [Richmond, 1957] [35] 1., processed.

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27. Barrow, W. J., and Reavis C. Sproull: "Permanence in Book Papers," *Science*, 129:1075-1084, April 24, 1959.

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64. Barrow, W. J.: *Improvement of Permanence and Durability of Book Papers, A Progress Report, June 24, 1959 - Sept. 15, 1959, to Council on Library Resources.* [Richmond], September 15, 1959. 32 1.

65. Church, Randolph W., editor: *Deterioration of Book Stock, Causes and Remedies: Two Studies on the Permanence of Book Paper Conducted by W. J. Barrow.* Richmond, The Virginia State Library, 1959. 70 pp.

International Organization of Effort

30. Carter, Edward: *International Organization in Librarianship and Documentation.* [Washington, 1958] 59 1., processed.

Libraries

Coordination of Reference Services

31. Krould, Harry J.: *An Inquiry on Aspects of Public Library Reference Service.* [Washington, 1958.] 2 v., typescript.

In the Soviet Union

32. Horecky, Paul L.: *Libraries and Bibliographic Centers in the Soviet Union.* [Bloomington: Indiana University Publications, © 1959.] xviii, 287 pp.

66. Gorokhoff, Boris I.: *Publishing in the U.S.S.R.* [Bloomington: Indiana University Publications, © 1959.]

xvi, 306 pp.

National

33. [Mumford, L. Quincy:] "Report from the Librarian of Congress [on the Seminar on National Libraries in Europe, Vienna, Sept. 1958]" *Library of Congress Information Bulletin* 17:611-612, October 27, 1958.

Space Problems

34. *Meeting to Plan Studies Toward the Solution of the Space Problems of Large (General) Research Libraries, Cosmos Club, Washington, D. C., October 27-28, 1958.* Washington: Council on Library Resources, Inc., 1958. 8 p. 1., processed. ("Corrigenda," 1 1.)

35. "Space Problems of Large (General) Research Libraries: Report of a Meeting," *College and Research Libraries* 20:217-220, May 1959.

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36. Assembly of State Librarians: *Summary Proceedings of the Assembly of State Librarians held at the Library of Congress, November 12-14, 1958.* Washington: Library of Congress, 1959. v., 45 pp., processed.

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68. Evans, Luther H.: "The Survey of Federal Departmental Libraries," *D. C. Libraries* 31: 2-8. January, 1960.

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40. — —: *1959 National Library Week. 2nd Annual Report.* [New York: The Committee, 1959.] [22] pp.

41. Parsons, Arthur H. Jr.: *Fountains, Not Reservoirs — The Public Library.* [Chicago: American Library Association, 1958.] 16 pp.

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42. University of Michigan. Engineering Research Institute: *Final Report: Application of a Telereference System to Divisional Library Card Catalogs; A Feasibility Analysis.* [Ann Arbor: The Institute. For] Council on Library Resources, Inc., 1958. 91 pp.

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Library of Congress Information Bulletin 18: 347-349, June 22, 1959.

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69. Ramo-Wooldridge, Thompson Ramo Wooldridge, Inc.: *Word Correlation and Automatic Indexing, Progress Report No. 1, C82-9U9, 21 September 1959*. Los Angeles, The Corporation, 1959. 24 l., processed.

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45. Taine, Seymour I.: "New Program for Indexing at the National Library of Medicine," *Bulletin of the Medical Library Association* 47:117-123. April, 1959.

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Equipment

47. Ballou, Hubbard W.: *Guide to Microreproduction Equipment*. Annapolis, National Microfilm Association, 1959. viii, 438 pp.

High Density Storage

72. AVCO Corporation, Crosley Division, Electronics Research Laboratories: *Technical Investigation of Elements of a Mechanized Library System, Special Report No. EW 6680-1, August 18, 1959*. Boston, The Corporation, 1959. 18 l., processed.

In Libraries

48. *Meeting on the Problems of Microform in Libraries, Cosmos Club, Washington, D. C., May 23, 1958; Summary of Discussions*. Washington: Council on Library Resources, Inc. [1958]. 12 l., processed.

Journal Publication

49. Herman, Carlton M.: "New Journal in Microform," *A.I.B.S. [American Institute of Biological Sciences] Bulletin*, 9: 31-33, January, 1959.

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51. *Wildlife Disease* no. 1 — [Washington: Wildlife Dis-

ease Association] January 1959. Quarterly; issued on Micro-cards with accompanying leaflet, *Abstracts from Wildlife Disease*.

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53. Radio Corporation of America. Development Engineering, Defense Electronic Products; *Design Plan for the Development of an Automatic Page Turner by Elbert Marsh, August 1958*. Camden, N. J., The Corporation, 1958. 25 l., 17 p1., processed.

Photosensitive Materials

54. Chalkley, Lyman: "Conditions for Projection Copying on Dye Cyanide Sensitized Materials," *Photographic Science and Engineering* 3:174-177. July-August, 1959.

Readers and Reading

55. *Reading for Life: Developing the College Student's Lifetime Reading Interest*. Edited with a Preface by Jacob M. Price. Ann Arbor: University of Michigan Press [c. 1959]. xi, 271 pp. (Record of the conference on "The Undergraduate and Life-Time Reading Interest," Ann Arbor, February 21-22, 1958.)

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73. International Conference on Scientific Information: *Proceedings of the . . . , Washington, D. C., November 16-21, 1958*. Washington, National Academy of Sciences-National Research Council, 1959. 2 v., 1639 pp.

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